

EIC User Group Newsletter

January 2020

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NEWS

- The best way to wish the entire EICUG community a **Happy New 2020** is to announce that the US Secretary of Energy **approved the CD-0** (“Approve Mission Need”) on Dec. 19th 2019, and that on Jan. 9th 2020 the US Department of Energy (DOE) **selected Brookhaven National Lab (BNL)** as the site for building the EIC. This is the [official announcement from DOE](#)
- The next **EICUG remote quarterly meeting** will be held on Jan. 23rd 2020, 10-12am EST. Agenda items will include: a) overview of recent EICUG organizational matters, b) update on EIC developments at BNL / JLab, c) EICUG Yellow Report status, d) EICUG Software overview. Details about connection links will be announced shortly before the event date.

- Following up with the [kick-off meeting held at MIT on Dec. 12-13 2019](#), the Steering Committee announced for the year 2020 four workshops towards the preparation of the **EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Studies**, the “**Yellow Report Workshops 2020**”. The dates and locations are:
 - 1st Workshop: 19-21 March 2020, Temple Univ. - Philadelphia (USA)
 - 2nd Workshop: 22-24 May 2020, Univ. and INFN - Pavia - Pavia (Italy)
 - 3rd Workshop: 17-19 September 2020, CUA - Washington D.C. (USA)
 - 4th Workshop: 19-21 November 2020, UCB - Berkeley (USA)**Eight Conveners** were **appointed** to coordinate these activities, four for the **Physics Working Group** (Adrian Dumitru, Olga Evdokimov, Andreas Metz, Carlos Munoz) and four for the **Detector Working Group** (Ken Barish, Tanja Horn, Peter Jones, Silvia Dalla Torre). Work is in progress to select Sub-Conveners for each identified sub-working group and to outline the milestones and plan the agenda accordingly. Please, visit the “Yellow Report” menu on the [EICUG web site](#) for more details.

NEWS from the SOFTWARE WORKING GROUP

A series of **EIC Software Tutorials** are being planned in parallel with the kick-off of the EIC Yellow Report efforts. On Jan. 9 2020 9am-6pm EST, an Introductory Tutorial to the JupyterLab workspace was held at JLab, including remote call-in. More is planned on Jan. 29 2020 at BNL and in February. BluJeans remote connection is also provided. See this [Indico page](#) for more details.

NEWS from the INSTITUTIONAL BOARD

- The EIC User Group (**EICUG**) is **growing!** We welcome the 8 institutions that joined the EICUG in the last weeks:
 - Pablo de Olavide University (Spain)
 - Sejong University (Korea)
 - National Institute of Technology, Jalandhar (India)
 - Institute of Physics (India)
 - Panjab University (India)
 - Indian Inst. for Sci. Educat. and Research (IISER), Berhampur (India)
 - Akal University (India)
 - Cockcroft Institute for Accelerator Science (UK)
 - Indian Inst. for Sci. Educat. and Research (IISER), Tirupati (India)

- The EIC User Group (**EICUG**) currently stands at 987 members, from 202 institutions in 30 countries. Theory members are approximately 25%, experimentalists 58%, experts in accelerators 15%, the remaining split into different expertise. Comparing with the time of submission of the EIC document to the European Strategy for Particle Physics Update (ESPPU), the EICUG has grown considerably: more than one year ago, it consisted of 837 members from 177 institutions in 30 countries. The splitting among theory, experiment, accelerator, was 20%, 58%, 17%, respectively, plus a 5% of various other expertise. Europe has always been the largest representative area after US. In the last year, the numbers changed as: from 237 to 252 members, from 59 to 64 institutions, theory from 28.5% to 31.5%, experiment from 68.5% to 63.5%, others from 3% to 5%.

NEWS from ELECTION and NOMINATION COMMITTEE

- The **term of Ernst Sichtermann** as “At Large Member” of the EICUG Steering Committee **ended** on Oct. 31 2019. It has been extended to Dec. 31st in order to coordinate elections in January and/or July of each year, as needed. Nominations have been called for with deadline Oct. 31 2019. **Two candidates** agreed to stand for election: **Haiyan Gao** (Duke University) and **Barbara Jacak** (Lawrence Berkeley National Lab and University of California, Berkeley). The election was open on Dec. 5th 2019, with voting done by Institutional Board members on behalf of their institutions. The **deadline has been extended to Jan. 17th 2020.**

NEWS from the CONFERENCE & TALKS COMMITTEE

- For **upcoming conferences** and workshops see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> . For a list of **open EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/open> . For a list of **previous EICUG talks** see <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (often including also a link to the presentation). If you wish to recommend a candidate, including yourself, or if in general you wish to suggest new speakers (including yourself) to be considered for future invitations, please contact the Conference & Talks Committee at eicug-talks@eicug.org . Here, you can find also the general [talks guidelines](#) .

RECENT WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/previous> (includes also links to some presentations)

[POETIC 2019](#), Berkeley (CA - USA), 16-20 September 2019

[Light Cone 2019](#), Palaiseau (France), 16-20 September 2019

[EIC Software meeting and GEANT4 Technical Forum](#), JLab Newport News (VA - USA), 24 September 2019

[13th European Research Conference on Electromagnetic Interactions with Nucleons and Nuclei](#), Paphos (Cyprus), 27 October - 2 November 2019

[CHEP 2019](#), Adelaide (Australia), 3-8 November 2019

[Quark Matter 2019](#), Wuhan (China), 4-8 November 2019

[EIC Streaming Readout workshop](#), BNL Upton (NY - USA), 13-15 November 2019

[LPC Workshop on Physics Connections the LHC and EIC](#), FermiLab (IL - USA), 13-15 November 2019

[Forward Physics and QCD at LHC](#), Guanajuato (Mexico), 18-23 November 2019

[MCEGs for future ep and eA facilities](#), Vienna (Austria), 20-22 November 2019

[Resummation, Evolution, Factorization \(REF 2019\)](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 November 2019

[CPAD Instrumentation Frontier Workshop](#), Madison (WI - USA), 8-10 December 2019

[EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Developments kick-off meeting](#), MIT - Boston (MA - USA), 12-13 December 2019

[International workshop on QCD with EIC \(QEIC\)](#), Bombay (India), 4-7 January 2020

UPCOMING WORKSHOPS/MEETINGS of INTEREST

See also <http://www.eicug.org/web/events/upcoming> and <http://cnr2.kent.edu/~manley/BRAGmeetings.html>

[Exploring QCD with light nuclei at EIC](#), Stony Brook (NY - US), 21-24 January 2020

[EIC Detector R&D Committee Meeting](#), Upton (NY - US), 30-31 January 2020

[Correlations in Partonic and Hadronic Interactions \(CPHI-2020\)](#), CERN-Geneva (Switzerland), 3-7 February 2020

[2020 Santa Fe Jets and Heavy Flavor Workshop](#), Santa Fe (NM - US), 3-5 February 2020

[Winter Workshop on Nuclear Dynamics](#), Puerto Vallarta (Mexico), 1-7 March 2020

[KEK Workshop on Femtotechnologies by quantum computers 2020](#), Tsukuba (Japan), 7 March 2020

[1st EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Philadelphia (MD-US), 19-21 March 2020

[DIS 2020](#), Brooklyn (NY - USA), 23-27 March 2020

[Rencontres de Moriond, QCD and high-energy interactions](#), La Thuile (Italy), 28 March - 4 April 2020

[Jet observables at an Electron Ion Collider](#), Upton (NY - US), 15-17 April 2020

[QCD Evolution 2020](#), Los Angeles (CA - US), 27 April - 1 May 2020

[Origin of the Visible Universe: Unraveling the Proton Mass \(INT-20-77W\)](#), INT Seattle (WA - US), 4 - 8 May 2020

[The 17th International Workshop on Hadron Structure and Spectroscopy](#), Trieste (Italy), 17-22 May 2020

[2nd EIC Physics and Detector Conceptual Development Workshop](#), Pavia (Italy), 22-24 May 2020

[Transversity 2020](#), Pavia (Italy), 25-29 May 2020

[Joint GlueX-PANDA-EIC Workshop on Machine Learning for Particle Physics Experiments](#), Darmstadt (Germany), 25-29 May 2020

[Hard Probes](#), Austin (TX - USA), 1-6 June 2020

[Tomography of light nuclei at an EIC](#), ECT*-Trento (Italy), 15-19 June 2020

[Light-Cone 2020](#), Jeju (Korea), 29 June - 4 July 2020

[40th International Conference on High Energy Physics \(ICHEP 2020\)](#), Prague (Czech Republic), 30 July - 5 August 2020

EIC Users Group Meeting 2020, Miami (F - USA), 3-7 August 2020

[Photonuclear Gordon Conference](#), Holderness (NH - USA), 9-14 August 2020

[22nd International Conference on Particles and Nuclei \(PANIC2020\)](#), Lisbon (Portugal), 31 August - 4 September 2020

[24th International Spin Symposium SPIN2020](#), Matsue (Japan), 20-25 September 2020

[Baryon 2020](#), Sevilla (Spain), 22-25 September 2020

[New Physics Phenomena - Hadronic Contributions to New Physics Searches](#), Crete (Greece), 24-30 September 2020

[Lepton-Photon 2021](#), Manchester (UK), 9-14 August 2021

Quarks and Nucleon Physics QNP 2021, Bonn (Germany), 20-24 September 2021